

Improving arithmetic calculations on elliptic curves with embedding degree $2^i.3$

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Abstract—Pairing-based cryptography offers a practical solution for achieving high level of security using more efficient and faster pairing-based techniques. However, achieving this level of security requires working with extension finite fields of the form \mathbb{F}_{p^k} where $k \geq 12$, making efficient implementation of these fields critical. This paper focuses on improving arithmetic calculations on elliptic curves with embedding degree of the form $2^i.3$. Our proposed approach utilizes the tower building technique. We explore all possible cases to find the optimal path by given the cost of arithmetic operations, we will give also a relationship between the operation cost and embedding degree, and finally reduce the squaring cost by 17%.

Index Terms—Elliptic curve, Pairing, Embedding degree, Twist curve, ...

I. INTRODUCTION

Pairing-based cryptography has been the focus of extensive research efforts, as developers and researchers seek to implement pairing protocols and algorithms more efficiently. Weil pairing was the first introduced by Weil Andre in 1948, followed by others such as Tate pairing, Ate pairing, and many more. Elliptic curve cryptosystems, discovered by Neal Koblitz [1] and Victor Miller [2], have been found to reduce the key sizes used in public key cryptography. Some works, such as the one presented in [3], are interested in digital signatures, while the authors in [4] prove the use of the final exponentiation in pairings as a countermeasure against fault attacks.

In recent years, researchers have explored working with elliptic curves of various embedding degrees. For instance, in [5], [6], [7], [13], Nadia El and others studied elliptic curves with embedding degrees 5, 9, 15, and 27. In [9], [10], [11], [12], and [13], researchers investigated working with curves of various embedding degrees. Additionally, in [8], the security level of optimal ate pairing is studied, and other useful works (see [5]) are also presented.

In this paper, we aim to develop efficient techniques to compute pairings for curves with embedding degree $2^i.3$. To achieve this, we use the tower-building technique to improve arithmetic operations in curves with embedding degree $2^i.3$. For other cases, such as 2^i , 3^j , $2^i.3^2$ and 2.3^3 , we have already investigated some of these cases for $k = 18, 36$, and 72 in previous articles [19], [20], and [21]. To provide some background for our investigation, Section 2 of this

paper recalls some mathematical background. In Section 3, we present our main theorem, which forms the basis of our investigation. Then, we present the results of our work, including improvements to arithmetic operations in $\mathbb{F}_{p^{2^i.3}}$ by making use of the tower-building technique. We also studying all possible cases, which demonstrate how using degree-2 or degree-3 twists can enable efficient handling of most operations in \mathbb{F}_{p^2} or \mathbb{F}_{p^3} . Finally, in Section 4, we conclude our paper by summarizing our main findings in this area.

II. MATHEMATICAL BACKGROUND

Throughout the paper, we assume that E is an elliptic curve with equation $y^2 = x^3 + ax + b$, where $b \in \mathbb{F}_q$ and q is a prime number. Additionally, we will use the following conventions without explicitly stating them

- k : the embedding degree: the smallest integer such that r divides $q^k - 1$.
- m, s, i : multiplication, squaring, inversion in field \mathbb{F}_p .
- M_i, S_i, I_i : multiplication, squaring, inversion in field \mathbb{F}_{p^i} .
- B_k : basis
- a_i : i is the position of point a in the basis B_k with $i \in \mathbb{N}$.
- b_j : j is the position of point b in the basis B_k with $j \in \mathbb{N}$.
- $P_l = (x_l, y_l) = (a_l, b_l)_{B_k}$: point in $E(\mathbb{F}_{p^k})$ with $l \in \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6\}$

Remark 1: In this paper, our main goal is to identify the optimal path with the lowest cost. Although the cost of multiplication remains the same in each path we choose, we aim to determine the path with the minimum cost of squaring or inversion.

Proposition 1: :

We investigate these cases by following the process outlined below:

- 1) Transform the elliptic curve with embedding degree k
- 2) Choose an appropriate irreducible polynomial for tower building
- 3) Construct the twisted isomorphic rational point
- 4) Determine the cost of multiplication, squaring, and inversion in the corresponding field.

TWIST OF AN ELLIPTIC CURVE

Definition 1: (Twist of an elliptic curve) [6]

Let E and E' be two elliptic curves defined over \mathbb{F}_q , for q , a power of a prime number p . Then, the curve E' is a twist of degree d of E if we can define an isomorphism Ψ_d over \mathbb{F}_{q^d} from E' into E and such that d is minimal:

$$\Psi_d : E'(\mathbb{F}_q) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{q^d}).$$

Theorem 1: [6] Let E be an elliptic curve defined by the short Weierstrass equation $y^2 = x^3 + ax + b$ over an extension \mathbb{F}_q of a finite field \mathbb{F}_p , for p a prime number, k a positive integer such that $q = p^k$. According to the value of k , the potential degrees for a twist are

$d = 2, 3, 4$ or 6 (in this paper, we are interested with the case of $d=2$ and 3).

- $d = 2$, Let $v \in \mathbb{F}_{p^{k/2}}$ such that the polynomial $X^2 - v$ is irreducible in $\mathbb{F}_{p^{k/2}}$. The equation of the curve E' defined on $\mathbb{F}_{p^{k/2}}$ is $E' : vy^2 = x^3 + ax + b$. The morphism Ψ_2 is defined by:

$$\begin{aligned} \Psi_2 : E'(\mathbb{F}_{p^{k/2}}) &\longrightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^k}) \\ (x, y) &\longrightarrow (x, yv^{1/2}) \end{aligned}$$

- $d = 3$, the curve E admits a twist of degree 3 if and only if $a = 0$. Let $v \in \mathbb{F}_{p^{k/3}}$ be such that the polynomial $X^3 - v$ is irreducible in $\mathbb{F}_{p^{k/3}}$. The equation of E' is then $y^2 = x^3 + \frac{b}{v}$. The morphism is:

$$\begin{aligned} \Psi_3 : E'(\mathbb{F}_{p^{k/3}}) &\longrightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^k}) \\ (x, y) &\longrightarrow (xv^{1/3}, yv^{1/2}) \end{aligned}$$

Calculation cost:

We use the cost of operation in Quadratic and cubic twisted curve to calculate the cost of operation in the field with embedding degree $2^i \cdot 3$ with the tower building technique for every path.

- Cost of operations in Quadratic twisted curve:

We already know that the cost of multiplication, squaring and inversion in the quadratic field \mathbb{F}_{p^2} are:

$$M_2 = 3m, S_2 = 2m, I_2 = 4m + i \text{ respectively ([17])}$$

- Cost of operations in Cubic twisted curve:

We already know that the cost of multiplication, squaring and inversion in in the cubic twisted field \mathbb{F}_{p^3} are:

$$M_3 = 6m, S_3 = 5s, I_3 = 9m + 2s + i \text{ respectively ([17]).}$$

Vector representation point:

In order to construct a vector representation point in \mathbb{F}_{p^k} , we generally need the following set forms a basis of \mathbb{F}_{p^k} over \mathbb{F}_p , $B_k = \{1, u, u^2, \dots, u^{k-1}\}$, which is known as polynomial basis. An arbitrary element A in \mathbb{F}_{p^k} is written as $A = a_0 + a_1u + a_2u^2 + \dots + a_{k-1}u^{k-1}$. The vector representation of A is $v_A = (a_0, a_1, a_2, \dots, a_{k-1})$.

We use the vector representation point of Quadratic and cubic twisted curve to know the vector representation point of operation in the field with embedding degree $2^i \cdot 3$ with the tower building technique for every path.

Vector representation point in Quadratic twisted curve:

We have E is $y^2 = x^3 + ax + b$.

Let $u \in \mathbb{F}_p$ such that the polynomial $x^2 - u$ is irreducible over \mathbb{F}_p .

The equation of E' is $uy^2 = x^3 + ax + b$.

So to map $E(\mathbb{F}_p)$ to $E'(\mathbb{F}_p)$, we have:

$$\begin{aligned} E(\mathbb{F}_p) &\rightarrow E'(\mathbb{F}_p) \\ (x, y) &\rightarrow (x_1, y_1) = (x, yu^{1/2}) \end{aligned}$$

Using $\psi_2(x, y) = (x, yu^{1/2})$ to map $E'(\mathbb{F}_p)$ to $E(\mathbb{F}_{p^2})$

$$\begin{aligned} E'(\mathbb{F}_p) &\rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^2}) \\ (x, y) &\rightarrow (x, yu^{1/2}) \end{aligned}$$

Hence, to map $E(\mathbb{F}_p)$ to $E(\mathbb{F}_{p^2})$, we have:

$$\begin{aligned} E(\mathbb{F}_p) &\rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^2}) \\ (x, y) &\rightarrow (x_1, y_1) = (x, yu) \end{aligned}$$

- Let map P to P_1 :

Let $P = (x, y) = (a, b)$ and $P_1 = (x_1, y_1) = (a_1, b_1)_{B_2}$, where $x_1, y_1, a_1, b_1 \in \mathbb{F}_{p^2}$.

P_1 has a special vector representation with 2 \mathbb{F}_p elements for each x_1 and y_1 coordinates. We have $B_2 = (1, u)$, $\psi_2 : E'(\mathbb{F}_p) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^2})$,

$\psi_2(x, y) = (x_1, y_1) = (x, yu)$, (see [9]) we have:

$$\begin{aligned} P &\rightarrow P_1 \\ E(\mathbb{F}_p) &\rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^2}) \\ (x, y) &\rightarrow (x_1, y_1) = (x, yu) = (a, bu)_{B_2} \\ P_1 &= (x_1, y_1) = (x, yu) = (a, bu)_{B_2} = ((a, 0), (0, b)) \end{aligned}$$

- Let remap P_1 to P : obtained easily by just placing a and b in the correct basis position.

$$\begin{aligned} P_1 &\rightarrow P \\ E(\mathbb{F}_{p^2}) &\rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_p) \\ (x_1, y_1) &\rightarrow (x, y) = (a, b) \\ P &= (x, y) = (a, b) \end{aligned}$$

So we can easily map and remap between P and P_1 .

Vector representation point in Cubic twisted curve:

The curve E admits a twist of degree 3 if and only if $a = 0$ i.e $y^2 = x^3 + b$.

Let $u \in \mathbb{F}_p$ such that the polynomial $x^3 - u$ is irreducible over \mathbb{F}_p .

The equation of E' is $y^2 = x^3 + b/u$.

So to map $E(\mathbb{F}_p)$ to $E'(\mathbb{F}_p)$, we have:

$$\begin{aligned} E(\mathbb{F}_p) &\rightarrow E'(\mathbb{F}_p) \\ (x, y) &\rightarrow (x_1, y_1) = (xu^{1/3}, yu^{1/2}) \end{aligned}$$

Using $\psi_3(x, y) = (xu^{2/3}, yu^{1/2})$ to map $E'(\mathbb{F}_p)$ to $E(\mathbb{F}_{p^3})$

$$\begin{aligned} E'(\mathbb{F}_p) &\rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^3}) \\ (x, y) &\rightarrow (xu^{2/3}, yu^{1/2}) \end{aligned}$$

Hence, to map $E(\mathbb{F}_p)$ to $E(\mathbb{F}_{p^3})$, we have:

$$E(\mathbb{F}_p) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^3})$$

$$(x, y) \rightarrow (x_1, y_1) = (xu, yu)$$

• Let map P to P_1 :

Let $P = (x, y) = (a, b)$ and $P_1 = (x_1, y_1) = (a_1, b_1)_{B_3}$, where $x_1, y_1, a_1, b_1 \in \mathbb{F}_{p^3}$.

P_1 has a special vector representation with 3 \mathbb{F}_p elements for each x_1 and y_1 coordinates.

We have $B_3 = (1, u, u^2)$, $\psi_3 : E'(\mathbb{F}_p) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^3})$, $\psi_3(x, y) = (x_1, y_1) = (xu, yu)$, (see [9]) we have:

$$P \rightarrow P_1$$

$$E(\mathbb{F}_p) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^3})$$

$$(x, y) \rightarrow (x_1, y_1) = (xu, yu) = (au, bu)_{B_3}$$

$$P_1 = (x_1, y_1) = (xu, yu) = (au, bu)_{B_3} = ((0, a, 0), (0, b, 0))$$

• Let remap P_1 to P: obtained easily by just placing a and b in the correct basis position

$$P_1 \rightarrow P$$

$$E(\mathbb{F}_{p^3}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_p)$$

$$(x_1, y_1) \rightarrow (x, y) = (a, b)$$

$$P = (x, y) = (a, b)$$

So we can easily map and remap between P and P_1 .

Corollary 1: :

We can do an extension for the above vector representation, we have:

$$E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{k/2}}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^k})$$

$$(x, y) \rightarrow (x, yu)$$

and,

$$E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{k/3}}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^k})$$

$$(x, y) \rightarrow (xu, yu)$$

III. TOWER BUILDING TECHNIQUE IN ELLIPTIC CURVE WITH EMBEDDING DEGREE $2^i \cdot 3$

In this section, we will study the elliptic curve with embedding degree $2^i \cdot 3 < 100$, i.e when $k=6, 12, 24, 48, 96$.

A. Sextic twisted curve

There are two paths to find the cost of squaring and inversion in this field:

• Path 1: let

$$\mathbb{F}_{p^2} = \mathbb{F}_p[u]/(u^2 - \beta) \text{ such that } \beta \text{ non square}$$

$$\mathbb{F}_{p^6} = \mathbb{F}_{p^2}[v]/(v^3 - u) \text{ such that } u \text{ non cube}$$

Hence, $v^3 = u$, so, $B_6 = \{1, v, v^2, \dots, v^5\} = \{1, v, v^2, u, uv, u^2v\}$

$$E(\mathbb{F}_p) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^2}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^6})$$

$$(x, y) \rightarrow (x_1, y_1) \rightarrow (vx_1, vy_1)$$

$$(x, y) \rightarrow (x, y) \rightarrow (vx, uvv)$$

$$P_2 = (x_2, y_2) = (vx, uvv) = (va, uvb)_{B_6}$$

$$= ((0, a, 0, 0, 0, 0), (0, 0, 0, 0, b, 0))$$

• Path 2: let

$$\mathbb{F}_{p^3} = \mathbb{F}_p[u]/(u^3 - \beta) \text{ such that } \beta \text{ non cube}$$

$$\mathbb{F}_{p^6} = \mathbb{F}_{p^3}[v]/(v^2 - u) \text{ such that } u \text{ non square}$$

Hence, $v^2 = u$, so, $B_6 = \{1, v, v^2, \dots, v^5\} = \{1, v, u, uv, u^2, u^2v\}$

$$E(\mathbb{F}_p) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^3}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^6})$$

$$(x, y) \rightarrow (x_1, y_1) \rightarrow (x_1, vy_1)$$

$$(x, y) \rightarrow (ux, uy) \rightarrow (ux, uvv)$$

$$P_2 = (x_2, y_2) = (ux, uvv) = (ua, uvb)_{B_6}$$

$$= ((0, 0, a, 0, 0, 0), (0, 0, 0, b, 0, 0))$$

Each rational point $P_2 \in E(\mathbb{F}_{p^6})$ has a special vector representation with 6 elements in \mathbb{F}_p for each x_2 and y_2 coordinates.

The cost of operations in the 6th twisted field \mathbb{F}_{p^6} are:

- The first path : $E(\mathbb{F}_p) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^2}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^6})$
 $M_6 = (M_2)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^3}} = (3m)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^3}} = 3M_3 = 18m$,
 $S_6 = (S_2)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^3}} = (2m)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^3}} = 2M_3 = 12m$,
 $I_6 = (I_2)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^3}} = (4m + i)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^3}} = 4M_3 + I_3 = 33m + 2s + i$.
- The second path : $E(\mathbb{F}_p) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^3}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^6})$
 $M_6 = (M_3)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = (6m)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = 6M_2 = 18m$,
 $S_6 = (S_3)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = (5s)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = 5S_2 = 10m$,
 $I_6 = (I_3)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = (9m + 2s + i)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = 9M_2 + 2S_2 + I_2 = 35m + i$.

TABLE I
COST OF OPERATIONS IN SEXTIC TWISTED CURVE

Path	Field	Operations	Cost of $M_{2,3}$	Cost of $S_{2,3}$	Cost of $I_{2,3}$
1	\mathbb{F}_{p^6}	M_6, S_6, I_6	18m	12m	33m+2s+i
2	\mathbb{F}_{p^6}	M_6, S_6, I_6	18m	10m	35m+i

In the table above we see that the cost of squaring in path 2 is less than the path 1, however the cost of inversion is more than path 1, after we subtract the overall cast of all operations, we find that the optimal path in this elliptic curve with embedding degree 6 is the second path.

B. 12th twisted curve

There are three paths to build extension in this field:

• Path 1: let

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{F}_{p^2} &= \mathbb{F}_p[u]/(u^2 - \beta) \text{ such that } \beta \text{ non square} \\ \mathbb{F}_{p^4} &= \mathbb{F}_{p^2}[v]/(v^2 - u) \text{ such that } u \text{ non square} \\ \mathbb{F}_{p^{12}} &= \mathbb{F}_{p^4}[t]/(t^3 - v) \text{ such that } v \text{ non cube} \end{aligned}$$

Hence, $t^3 = v$ and $v^2 = u$, so, $t^6 = v^2 = u$, so,
 $B_{12} = \{1, t, t^2, \dots, t^{11}\}$
 $\{1, t, t^2, v, vt, vt^2, u, ut, ut^2, uv, uvt, uv^2\}$

$$\begin{aligned} E(\mathbb{F}_p) &\longrightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^2}) \longrightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^4}) \longrightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{12}}) \\ (x, y) &\longrightarrow (x_1, y_1) \longrightarrow (x_2, y_2) \longrightarrow (tx_2, ty_2) \\ (x, y) &\longrightarrow (x, uy) \longrightarrow (x, uvy) \longrightarrow (tx, uvt y) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} P_3 &= (x_3, y_3) = (tx, uvt y) = (ta, uvtb)_{B_{12}} \\ &= ((0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, a, 0), (0, b, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0)) \end{aligned}$$

• Path 2: let

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{F}_{p^2} &= \mathbb{F}_p[u]/(u^2 - \beta) \text{ such that } \beta \text{ non square} \\ \mathbb{F}_{p^6} &= \mathbb{F}_{p^2}[v]/(v^3 - u) \text{ such that } u \text{ non cube} \\ \mathbb{F}_{p^{12}} &= \mathbb{F}_{p^6}[t]/(t^2 - v) \text{ such that } v \text{ non square} \end{aligned}$$

Hence, $t^2 = v$ and $v^3 = u$, so, $t^6 = v^3 = u$, so,
 $B_{12} = \{1, t, t^2, \dots, t^{11}\}$
 $\{1, t, v, vt, v^2, v^2t, u, ut, uv, uvt, uv^2, uv^2t\}$

$$\begin{aligned} E(\mathbb{F}_p) &\longrightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^2}) \longrightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^6}) \longrightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{12}}) \\ (x, y) &\longrightarrow (x_1, y_1) \longrightarrow (x_2, y_2) \longrightarrow (x_2, ty_2) \\ (x, y) &\longrightarrow (x, uy) \longrightarrow (vx, uvy) \longrightarrow (vx, uvt y) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} P_3 &= (x_3, y_3) = (vx, uvt y) = (va, uvtb)_{B_{12}} \\ &= ((0, 0, a, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0), (0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, b, 0, 0)) \end{aligned}$$

• Path 3: let

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{F}_{p^3} &= \mathbb{F}_p[u]/(u^3 - \beta) \text{ such that } \beta \text{ non cube} \\ \mathbb{F}_{p^6} &= \mathbb{F}_{p^3}[v]/(v^2 - u) \text{ such that } u \text{ non square} \\ \mathbb{F}_{p^{12}} &= \mathbb{F}_{p^6}[t]/(t^2 - v) \text{ such that } v \text{ non square} \end{aligned}$$

Hence, $t^2 = v$ and $v^2 = u$, so, $t^4 = v^2 = u$, so,
 $B_{12} = \{1, t, t^2, \dots, t^{11}\}$
 $\{1, t, v, vt, u, ut, uv, uvt, u^2, u^2t, u^2v, u^2vt\}$

$$\begin{aligned} E(\mathbb{F}_p) &\longrightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^3}) \longrightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^6}) \longrightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{12}}) \\ (x, y) &\longrightarrow (x_1, y_1) \longrightarrow (x_2, y_2) \longrightarrow (x_2, ty_2) \\ (x, y) &\longrightarrow (ux, uy) \longrightarrow (ux, uvy) \longrightarrow (ux, uvt y) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} P_3 &= (x_3, y_3) = (ux, uvt y) = (ua, uvtb)_{B_{12}} \\ &= ((0, 0, 0, 0, a, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0), (0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, b, 0, 0, 0)) \end{aligned}$$

Each rational point $P_3 \in E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{12}})$ has a special vector representation with 12 elements in \mathbb{F}_p for each x_3 and y_3 coordinates.

The cost of operations in in the 12th twisted field $\mathbb{F}_{p^{12}}$ are:

- First path: $E(\mathbb{F}_p) \longrightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^2}) \longrightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^4}) \longrightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{12}})$
 $M_{12} = (M_4)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^3}} = (9m)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^3}} = 9M_3 = 54m,$
 $S_{12} = (S_4)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^3}} = (6m)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^3}} = 6M_3 = 36m,$
 $I_{12} = (I_4)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^3}} = (16m + i)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^3}} = 16M_3 + I_3 = 105m + 2s + i.$
- Second path: $E(\mathbb{F}_p) \longrightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^2}) \longrightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^6}) \longrightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{12}})$
 $M_{12} = (M_6)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = (18m)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = 18M_2 = 54m,$
 $S_{12} = (S_6)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = (12m)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = 12M_2 = 36m,$
 $I_{12} = (I_6)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = (33m + 2s + i)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = 33M_2 + 2S_2 + I_2 = 107m + i.$
- Third path: $E(\mathbb{F}_p) \longrightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^3}) \longrightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^6}) \longrightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{12}})$
 $M_{12} = (M_6)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = (18m)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = 18M_2 = 54m,$
 $S_{12} = (S_6)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = (10m)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = 10M_2 = 30m,$
 $I_{12} = (I_6)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = (35m + i)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = 35M_2 + I_2 = 109m + i.$

TABLE II
COST OF OPERATIONS IN 12th TWISTED CURVE

	Field	Operations	Cost of $M_{2,2,3}$	Cost of $S_{2,2,3}$	Cost of $I_{2,2,3}$
1	$\mathbb{F}_{p^{12}}$	M_{12}, S_{12}, I_{12}	54m	36m	105m+2s+i
2	$\mathbb{F}_{p^{12}}$	M_{12}, S_{12}, I_{12}	54m	36m	107m+i
3	$\mathbb{F}_{p^{12}}$	M_{12}, S_{12}, I_{12}	54m	30m	109m+i

In the table above, we see that the cost of squaring in path 3 is less than the path 1, however the cost of inversion is more than path 1, after we subtract the overall cost of all operations, we find that the optimal path in this elliptic curve with embedding degree 12 is the third path.

C. 24th twisted curve

There are four paths to build extension in the field of $\mathbb{F}_{p^{24}}$:

• Path 1:

Let

$$\mathbb{F}_{p^2} = \mathbb{F}_p[u]/(u^2 - \beta) \text{ such that } \beta \text{ non square}$$

$$\mathbb{F}_{p^4} = \mathbb{F}_{p^2}[v]/(v^2 - u) \text{ such that } u \text{ non square}$$

$$\mathbb{F}_{p^8} = \mathbb{F}_{p^4}[t]/(t^2 - v) \text{ such that } v \text{ non square}$$

$$\mathbb{F}_{p^{24}} = \mathbb{F}_{p^8}[w]/(w^3 - t) \text{ such that } t \text{ non cube}$$

Hence, $w^3 = t$, $t^2 = v$ and $v^2 = u$, so, $w^{12} = t^4 = v^2 = u$, so,

$$B_{24} = \{1, w, w^2, \dots, w^{23}\}$$

$$= \{1, w, w^2, t, tw, tw^2, v, vw, vw^2, vt, vtw, vtw^2, u, \dots, uvw^{23}\}$$

$$E(\mathbb{F}_p) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^2}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^4}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^8}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{24}})$$

$$(x, y) \rightarrow (x_1, y_1) \rightarrow (x_2, y_2) \rightarrow (x_3, y_3) \rightarrow (wx_3, wy_3)$$

$$(x, y) \rightarrow (x, uy) \rightarrow (x, uv y) \rightarrow (x, uvty) \rightarrow (wx, uvtwy)$$

$$P_4 = (x_4, y_4) = (wx, uvtwy) = (wa, uvtwb)_{B_{24}} = ((0, a, 0, \dots, 0), (0, \dots, 0, b, 0, 0))$$

• Path 2:

Let

$$\mathbb{F}_{p^2} = \mathbb{F}_p[u]/(u^2 - \beta) \text{ such that } \beta \text{ non square}$$

$$\mathbb{F}_{p^4} = \mathbb{F}_{p^2}[v]/(v^2 - u) \text{ such that } u \text{ non square}$$

$$\mathbb{F}_{p^{12}} = \mathbb{F}_{p^4}[t]/(t^3 - v) \text{ such that } v \text{ non cube}$$

$$\mathbb{F}_{p^{24}} = \mathbb{F}_{p^{12}}[w]/(w^2 - t) \text{ such that } t \text{ non square}$$

Hence, $w^2 = t$, $t^3 = v$ and $v^2 = u$, so, $w^{12} = t^6 = v^2 = u$, so,

$$B_{24} = \{1, w, w^2, \dots, w^{23}\}$$

$$= \{1, w, t, tw, t^2, t^2w, v, vw, vt, vtw, vt^2, vt^2w, \dots, uvw^{23}\}$$

$$E(\mathbb{F}_p) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^2}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^4}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{12}}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{24}})$$

$$(x, y) \rightarrow (x_1, y_1) \rightarrow (x_2, y_2) \rightarrow (x_3, y_3) \rightarrow (x_3, wy_3)$$

$$(x, y) \rightarrow (x, uy) \rightarrow (x, uv y) \rightarrow (tx, uvty) \rightarrow (tx, uvtwy)$$

$$P_4 = (x_4, y_4) = (tx, uvtwy) = (ta, uvtwb)_{B_{24}} = ((0, 0, a, 0, \dots, 0), (0, \dots, 0, b, 0, 0))$$

• Path 3:

Let

$$\mathbb{F}_{p^2} = \mathbb{F}_p[u]/(u^2 - \beta) \text{ such that } \beta \text{ non square}$$

$$\mathbb{F}_{p^6} = \mathbb{F}_{p^2}[v]/(v^3 - u) \text{ such that } u \text{ non cube}$$

$$\mathbb{F}_{p^{12}} = \mathbb{F}_{p^6}[t]/(t^2 - v) \text{ such that } v \text{ non square}$$

$$\mathbb{F}_{p^{24}} = \mathbb{F}_{p^{12}}[w]/(w^2 - t) \text{ such that } t \text{ non square}$$

Hence, $w^2 = t$, $t^2 = v$ and $v^3 = u$, so, $w^{12} = t^6 = v^3 = u$, so,

$$B_{24} = \{1, w, w^2, \dots, w^{23}\}$$

$$= \{1, w, t, tw, v, vw, vt, vtw, v^2, v^2w, v^2t, v^2tw, u, \dots, uvw^{23}\}$$

$$E(\mathbb{F}_p) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^2}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^6}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{12}}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{24}})$$

$$(x, y) \rightarrow (x_1, y_1) \rightarrow (x_2, y_2) \rightarrow (x_3, y_3) \rightarrow (x_3, wy_3)$$

$$(x, y) \rightarrow (x, uy) \rightarrow (vx, uv y) \rightarrow (vx, uvty) \rightarrow (vx, uvtwy)$$

$$P_4 = (x_4, y_4) = (vx, uvtwy) = (va, uvtwb)_{B_{24}} = ((0, 0, 0, 0, a, 0, \dots, 0), (0, \dots, 0, b, 0, 0, 0, 0))$$

• Path 4: Let

$$\mathbb{F}_{p^3} = \mathbb{F}_p[u]/(u^3 - \beta) \text{ such that } \beta \text{ non cube}$$

$$\mathbb{F}_{p^6} = \mathbb{F}_{p^3}[v]/(v^2 - u) \text{ such that } u \text{ non square}$$

$$\mathbb{F}_{p^{12}} = \mathbb{F}_{p^6}[t]/(t^2 - v) \text{ such that } v \text{ non square}$$

$$\mathbb{F}_{p^{24}} = \mathbb{F}_{p^{12}}[w]/(w^2 - t) \text{ such that } t \text{ non square}$$

Hence, $w^2 = t$, $t^2 = v$ and $v^2 = u$, so, $w^8 = t^4 = v^2 = u$, so,

$$B_{24} = \{1, w, w^2, \dots, w^{23}\} = \{1, w, t, tw, v, vw, vt, vtw, u, uv, ut, utw, uv, uvw, uvty, uvtyw, \dots, u^2vtw\}$$

$$E(\mathbb{F}_p) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^3}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^6}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{12}}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{24}})$$

$$(x, y) \rightarrow (x_1, y_1) \rightarrow (x_2, y_2) \rightarrow (x_3, y_3) \rightarrow (x_3, wy_3)$$

$$(x, y) \rightarrow (ux, uy) \rightarrow (ux, uv y) \rightarrow (ux, uvty) \rightarrow (ux, uvtwy)$$

$$P_4 = (x_4, y_4) = (ux, uvtwy) = (ua, uvtwb)_{B_{24}}$$

$$= ((0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, a, 0, \dots, 0), (0, \dots, 0, b, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0))$$

Each rational point $P_4 \in E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{24}})$ has a special vector representation with 24 elements in \mathbb{F}_p for each x_4 and y_4 coordinates.

The cost of operations in in the 24th twisted field $\mathbb{F}_{p^{24}}$ are:

• First path:

$$E(\mathbb{F}_p) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^2}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^4}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^8}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{24}})$$

$$M_{24} = (M_8)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^3}} = (27m)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^3}} = 27M_3 = 162m,$$

$$S_{24} = (S_8)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^3}} = (18m)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^3}} = 18M_3 = 108m,$$

$$I_{24} = (I_8)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^3}} = (52m + i)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^3}} = 52M_3 + I_3 = 321m + 2s + i.$$

• Second path:

$$E(\mathbb{F}_p) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^2}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^4}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{12}}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{24}})$$

$$M_{24} = (M_{12})_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = (54m)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = 54M_2 = 162m,$$

$$S_{24} = (S_{12})_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = (36m)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = 36M_2 = 108m,$$

$$I_{24} = (I_{12})_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = (105m + 2s + i)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = 105M_2 + 2S_2 + I_2 = 323m + 2s + i.$$

• Third path:

$$E(\mathbb{F}_p) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^2}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^6}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{12}}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{24}})$$

$$M_{24} = (M_{12})_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = (54m)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = 54M_2 = 162m,$$

$$S_{24} = (S_{12})_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = (36m)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = 36M_2 = 108m,$$

$$I_{24} = (I_{12})_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = (107m + i)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = 107M_2 + I_2 = 325m + i.$$

• Fourth path:

$$E(\mathbb{F}_p) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^3}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^6}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{12}}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{24}})$$

$$M_{24} = (M_{12})_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = (54m)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = 54M_2 = 162m,$$

$$S_{24} = (S_{12})_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = (30m)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = 30M_2 = 90m,$$

$$I_{24} = (I_{12})_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = (109m + i)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = 109M_2 + I_2 = 331m + i.$$

TABLE III
COST OF OPERATIONS IN THE 24th TWISTED CURVE

	Field	Operations	Cost of $M_{23,3}$	$S_{23,3}$	Cost of $I_{23,3}$
1	$\mathbb{F}_{p^{24}}$	M_{24}, S_{24}, I_{24}	162m	108m	321m+2s+i
2	\mathbb{F}_{p^6}	M_{24}, S_{24}, I_{24}	162m	108m	323m+2s+i
3	\mathbb{F}_{p^8}	M_{24}, S_{24}, I_{24}	162m	108m	325m+i
4	\mathbb{F}_{p^4}	M_{24}, S_{24}, I_{24}	162m	90m	331m+i

In the table above, we see that the cost of squaring in path 4 is less than the path 1, however the cost of inversion is more than path 1, after we subtract the overall cost of all operations, we find that the optimal path in this elliptic curve with embedding degree 24 is the fourth path.

D. 48th twisted curve

There are five paths to find the cost of inversion in this field is:

• Path 1: Let

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{F}_{p^2} &= \mathbb{F}_p[u]/(u^2 - \beta) \text{ such that } \beta \text{ non square} \\ \mathbb{F}_{p^4} &= \mathbb{F}_{p^2}[v]/(v^2 - u) \text{ such that } u \text{ non square} \\ \mathbb{F}_{p^8} &= \mathbb{F}_{p^4}[t]/(t^2 - v) \text{ such that } v \text{ non square} \\ \mathbb{F}_{p^{16}} &= \mathbb{F}_{p^8}[w]/(w^2 - t) \text{ such that } t \text{ non square} \\ \mathbb{F}_{p^{48}} &= \mathbb{F}_{p^{16}}[z]/(z^3 - w) \text{ such that } w \text{ non cube} \end{aligned}$$

Hence, $z^3 = w, w^2 = t, t^2 = v$ and $v^2 = u$, so, $z^{24} = w^8 = t^4 = v^2 = u$, so,

$$B_{48} = \{1, z, z^2, \dots, w^{47}\} = \{1, z, z^2, w, wz, wz^2, t, tz, tz^2, tw, twz, \dots, wtwz^2\}$$

$$\begin{aligned} E(\mathbb{F}_p) &\rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^2}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^4}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^8}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{16}}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{48}}) \\ (x, y) &\rightarrow (x_1, y_1) \rightarrow (x_2, y_2) \rightarrow (x_3, y_3) \rightarrow (x_4, y_4) \rightarrow (zx_4, zy_4) \\ (x, y) &\rightarrow (x, uy) \rightarrow (x, uvy) \rightarrow (x, uvt y) \rightarrow (x, uvtw y) \rightarrow (zx, uvtwzy) \end{aligned}$$

$$P_5 = (x_5, y_5) = (zx, uvtwzy) = (za, uvtwzb)_{B_{48}} = ((0, a, 0, \dots, 0), (0, \dots, 0, b, 0))$$

• Path 2: Let

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{F}_{p^2} &= \mathbb{F}_p[u]/(u^2 - \beta) \text{ such that } \beta \text{ non square} \\ \mathbb{F}_{p^4} &= \mathbb{F}_{p^2}[v]/(v^2 - u) \text{ such that } u \text{ non square} \\ \mathbb{F}_{p^8} &= \mathbb{F}_{p^4}[t]/(t^2 - v) \text{ such that } v \text{ non square} \\ \mathbb{F}_{p^{24}} &= \mathbb{F}_{p^8}[w]/(w^3 - t) \text{ such that } t \text{ non cube} \\ \mathbb{F}_{p^{48}} &= \mathbb{F}_{p^{24}}[z]/(z^2 - w) \text{ such that } w \text{ non square} \end{aligned}$$

Hence, $z^2 = w, w^3 = t, t^2 = v$ and $v^2 = u$, so, $z^{24} = w^{12} = t^4 = v^2 = u$, so,

$$B_{48} = \{1, z, z^2, \dots, w^{47}\} = \{1, z, w, wz, w^2, w^2z, t, \dots, wtw^2z\}$$

$$\begin{aligned} E(\mathbb{F}_p) &\rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^2}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^4}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^8}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{24}}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{48}}) \\ (x, y) &\rightarrow (x_1, y_1) \rightarrow (x_2, y_2) \rightarrow (x_3, y_3) \rightarrow (x_4, y_4) \rightarrow (x_4, zy_4) \\ (x, y) &\rightarrow (x, uy) \rightarrow (x, uvy) \rightarrow (x, uvt y) \rightarrow (wx, uvtw y) \rightarrow (wx, uvtwzy) \end{aligned}$$

$$P_5 = (x_5, y_5) = (wx, uvtwzy) = (wa, uvtwzb)_{B_{48}} = ((0, 0, a, 0, \dots, 0), (0, \dots, 0, b, 0, 0))$$

• Path 3: Let

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{F}_{p^2} &= \mathbb{F}_p[u]/(u^2 - \beta) \text{ such that } \beta \text{ non square} \\ \mathbb{F}_{p^4} &= \mathbb{F}_{p^2}[v]/(v^2 - u) \text{ such that } u \text{ non square} \\ \mathbb{F}_{p^{12}} &= \mathbb{F}_{p^4}[t]/(t^3 - v) \text{ such that } v \text{ non cube} \\ \mathbb{F}_{p^{24}} &= \mathbb{F}_{p^{12}}[w]/(w^2 - t) \text{ such that } t \text{ non square} \\ \mathbb{F}_{p^{48}} &= \mathbb{F}_{p^{24}}[z]/(z^2 - w) \text{ such that } w \text{ non square} \end{aligned}$$

Hence, $z^2 = w, w^2 = t, t^3 = v$ and $v^2 = u$, so, $z^{24} = w^{12} = t^6 = v^2 = u$, so,

$$B_{48} = \{1, z, z^2, \dots, w^{47}\} = \{1, z, w, wz, t, tz, tw, twz, t^2, \dots, wtw^2wz\}$$

$$\begin{aligned} E(\mathbb{F}_p) &\rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^2}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^4}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{12}}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{24}}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{48}}) \\ (x, y) &\rightarrow (x_1, y_1) \rightarrow (x_2, y_2) \rightarrow (x_3, y_3) \rightarrow (x_4, y_4) \rightarrow (x_4, zy_4) \\ (x, y) &\rightarrow (x, uy) \rightarrow (x, uvy) \rightarrow (tx, uvt y) \rightarrow (tx, uvtw y) \rightarrow (tx, uvtwzy) \end{aligned}$$

$$P_5 = (x_5, y_5) = (tx, uvtwzy) = (ta, uvtwzb)_{B_{48}} = ((0, 0, 0, 0, a, 0, \dots, 0), (0, \dots, 0, b, 0, 0, 0, 0))$$

• Path 4: Let

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{F}_{p^2} &= \mathbb{F}_p[u]/(u^2 - \beta) \text{ such that } \beta \text{ non square} \\ \mathbb{F}_{p^6} &= \mathbb{F}_{p^2}[v]/(v^3 - u) \text{ such that } u \text{ non cube} \\ \mathbb{F}_{p^{12}} &= \mathbb{F}_{p^6}[t]/(t^2 - v) \text{ such that } v \text{ non square} \\ \mathbb{F}_{p^{24}} &= \mathbb{F}_{p^{12}}[w]/(w^2 - t) \text{ such that } t \text{ non square} \\ \mathbb{F}_{p^{48}} &= \mathbb{F}_{p^{24}}[z]/(z^2 - w) \text{ such that } w \text{ non square} \end{aligned}$$

Hence, $z^2 = w, w^2 = t, t^2 = v$ and $v^3 = u$, so, $z^{24} = w^{12} = t^6 = v^3 = u$, so,

$$B_{48} = \{1, z, z^2, \dots, w^{47}\} = \{1, z, w, wz, t, tz, tw, twz, v, \dots, w^2twz\}$$

$$\begin{aligned} E(\mathbb{F}_p) &\rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^2}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^6}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{12}}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{24}}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{48}}) \\ (x, y) &\rightarrow (x_1, y_1) \rightarrow (x_2, y_2) \rightarrow (x_3, y_3) \rightarrow (x_4, y_4) \rightarrow (x_4, zy_4) \\ (x, y) &\rightarrow (x, uy) \rightarrow (vx, uvy) \rightarrow (vx, uvt y) \rightarrow (vx, uvtw y) \rightarrow (vx, uvtwzy) \end{aligned}$$

$$P_5 = (x_5, y_5) = (vx, uvtwzy) = (va, uvtwzb)_{B_{48}}$$

$$= ((0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, a, 0, \dots, 0), (0, \dots, 0, b_{40}, 0, \dots, 0))$$

• Path 5: Let

$$\mathbb{F}_{p^3} = \mathbb{F}_p[u]/(u^3 - \beta) \text{ such that } \beta \text{ non cube}$$

$$\mathbb{F}_{p^6} = \mathbb{F}_{p^3}[v]/(v^2 - u) \text{ such that } u \text{ non square}$$

$$\mathbb{F}_{p^{12}} = \mathbb{F}_{p^6}[t]/(t^2 - v) \text{ such that } v \text{ non square}$$

$$\mathbb{F}_{p^{24}} = \mathbb{F}_{p^{12}}[w]/(w^2 - t) \text{ such that } t \text{ non square}$$

$$\mathbb{F}_{p^{48}} = \mathbb{F}_{p^{24}}[z]/(z^2 - w) \text{ such that } w \text{ non square}$$

Hence, $z^2 = w, w^2 = t, t^2 = v$ and $v^2 = u$, so, $z^{16} = w^8 = t^4 = v^2 = u$, so,

$$B_{48} = \{1, z, z^2, \dots, w^{47}\}$$

$$\{1, 1, z, w, wz, t, tz, tw, twz, v, \dots, u^2vtwz\}$$

$$E(\mathbb{F}_p) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^3}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^6}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{12}}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{24}}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{48}})$$

$$(x, y) \rightarrow (x_1, y_1) \rightarrow (x_2, y_2) \rightarrow (x_3, y_3) \rightarrow (x_4, y_4) \rightarrow (x_4, zy_4)$$

$$(x, y) \rightarrow (ux, uy) \rightarrow (ux, uvy) \rightarrow (ux, uvtv) \rightarrow (ux, uvtw) \rightarrow (ux, uvtwzy)$$

$$P_5 = (x_5, y_5) = (ux, uvtwzy) = (ua, uvtwzb)_{B_{48}}$$

$$= ((0, \dots, 0, a_{17}, 0, \dots, 0), (0, \dots, 0, b_{30}, 0, \dots, 0))$$

Each rational point $P_5 \in \mathbb{G}_2 \subset E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{48}})$ has a special vector representation with 48 elements in \mathbb{F}_p for each x_i^5 and y_i^5 coordinates.

The cost of operations in in the 48th twisted field $\mathbb{F}_{p^{48}}$ are:

• First path:

$$E(\mathbb{F}_p) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^2}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^4}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^8}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{16}}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{48}})$$

$$M_{48} = (M_{16})_{\mathbb{F}_{p^3}} = (81m)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^3}} = 81M_3 = 486m,$$

$$S_{48} = (S_{16})_{\mathbb{F}_{p^3}} = (54m)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^3}} = 54M_3 = 324m,$$

$$I_{48} = (I_{16})_{\mathbb{F}_{p^3}} = (160m + i)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^3}} = 160M_3 + I_3 = 969m + 2s + i.$$

• Second path:

$$E(\mathbb{F}_p) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^2}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^4}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^8}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{24}}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{48}})$$

$$M_{48} = (M_{24})_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = (162m)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = 162M_2 = 486m,$$

$$S_{48} = (S_{24})_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = (108m)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = 108M_2 = 324m,$$

$$I_{48} = (I_{24})_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = (321m + 2s + i)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = 160M_3 + I_3 = 971m + i.$$

• Third path:

$$E(\mathbb{F}_p) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^2}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^4}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{12}}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{24}}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{48}})$$

$$M_{48} = (M_{24})_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = (162m)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = 162M_2 = 486m,$$

$$S_{48} = (S_{24})_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = (108m)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = 108M_2 = 324m,$$

$$I_{48} = (I_{24})_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = (323m + 2s + i)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = 323M_2 + 2S_2 + I_2 = 977m + i.$$

• Fourth path:

$$E(\mathbb{F}_p) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^2}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^6}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{12}}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{24}}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{48}})$$

$$M_{48} = (M_{24})_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = (162m)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = 81M_3 = 486m,$$

$$S_{48} = (S_{24})_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = (108m)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = 54M_3 = 324m,$$

$$I_{48} = (I_{24})_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = (325m + i)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = 325M_2 + I_2 = 979m + i.$$

• Fifth path:

$$E(\mathbb{F}_p) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^3}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^6}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{12}}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{24}}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{48}})$$

$$M_{48} = (M_{24})_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = (162m)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = 162M_2 = 486m,$$

$$S_{48} = (S_{24})_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = (90m)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = 90M_2 = 270m,$$

$$I_{48} = (I_{24})_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = (331m + i)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = 331M_2 + I_1 = 997m + i.$$

TABLE IV
COST OF OPERATIONS IN THE 48th TWISTED CURVE

	Field	Operations	$M_{2^4,3}$	$S_{2^4,3}$	Cost of $I_{2^4,3}$
1	$\mathbb{F}_{p^{48}}$	M_{48}, S_{48}, I_{48}	486m	324m	969m+2s+i
2	$\mathbb{F}_{p^{48}}$	M_{48}, S_{48}, I_{48}	486m	324m	971m+i
3	$\mathbb{F}_{p^{48}}$	M_{48}, S_{48}, I_{48}	486m	324m	977m+i
4	$\mathbb{F}_{p^{48}}$	M_{48}, S_{48}, I_{48}	486m	324m	979m+i
5	$\mathbb{F}_{p^{48}}$	M_{48}, S_{48}, I_{48}	486m	270m	997m+i

In the table above, we see that the cost of squaring in path 5 is less than the path 1, however the cost of inversion is more than path 1, after we subtract the overall cost of all operations, we find that the optimal path in this elliptic curve with embedding degree 48 is the fifth path.

E. 96th twisted curve

There are six paths to build the extension field $\mathbb{F}_{p^{96}}$:

• Path 1: Let

$$\mathbb{F}_{p^2} = \mathbb{F}_p[u]/(u^2 - \beta) \text{ such that } \beta \text{ non square}$$

$$\mathbb{F}_{p^4} = \mathbb{F}_{p^2}[v]/(v^2 - u) \text{ such that } u \text{ non square}$$

$$\mathbb{F}_{p^8} = \mathbb{F}_{p^4}[t]/(t^2 - v) \text{ such that } v \text{ non square}$$

$$\mathbb{F}_{p^{16}} = \mathbb{F}_{p^8}[w]/(w^2 - t) \text{ such that } t \text{ non square}$$

$$\mathbb{F}_{p^{32}} = \mathbb{F}_{p^{16}}[z]/(z^2 - w) \text{ such that } w \text{ non square}$$

$$\mathbb{F}_{p^{96}} = \mathbb{F}_{p^{32}}[c]/(c^3 - z) \text{ such that } z \text{ non cube}$$

Hence, $c^3 = z, z^2 = w, w^2 = t, t^2 = v$ and $v^2 = u$, so, $c^{48} = z^{16} = w^8 = t^4 = v^2 = u$, so,

$$B_{96} = \{1, c, c^2, \dots, c^{95}\}$$

$$= \{1, c, c^2, z, zc, zc^2, w, \dots, uvtwzc^2\}$$

$$E(\mathbb{F}_{p^2}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^4}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^8}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{16}}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{32}}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{96}})$$

$$(x_1, y_1) \rightarrow (x_2, y_2) \rightarrow (x_3, y_3) \rightarrow (x_4, y_4) \rightarrow (x_5, y_5) \rightarrow (cx^5, cy^5)$$

$$(x, uy) \rightarrow (x, uvy) \rightarrow (x, uvtv) \rightarrow (x, uvtw) \rightarrow (x, uvtwzy)$$

$$\rightarrow (cx, uvtwzcy)$$

$$P_6 = (x_6, y_6) = (cx, uvtwzcy) = (ca, uvtwzcb)_{B_{96}}$$

$$= ((0, a, 0, \dots, 0), (0, \dots, 0, b, 0))$$

• Path 2: Let

$$\mathbb{F}_{p^2} = \mathbb{F}_p[u]/(u^2 - \beta) \text{ such that } \beta \text{ non square}$$

$$\mathbb{F}_{p^4} = \mathbb{F}_{p^2}[v]/(v^2 - u) \text{ such that } u \text{ non square}$$

$$\mathbb{F}_{p^8} = \mathbb{F}_{p^4}[t]/(t^2 - v) \text{ such that } v \text{ non square}$$

$$\mathbb{F}_{p^{16}} = \mathbb{F}_{p^8}[w]/(w^2 - t) \text{ such that } t \text{ non square}$$

$$\mathbb{F}_{p^{48}} = \mathbb{F}_{p^{16}}[z]/(z^3 - w) \text{ such that } w \text{ non cube}$$

$$\mathbb{F}_{p^{96}} = \mathbb{F}_{p^{48}}[c]/(c^2 - z) \text{ such that } z \text{ non square}$$

Hence, $c^2 = z, z^3 = w, w^2 = t, t^2 = v$ and $v^2 = u$, so, $c^{48} = z^{24} = w^8 = t^4 = v^2 = u$, so,

$$B_{96} = \{1, c, c^2, \dots, c^{95}\}$$

$$= \{1, c, z, zc, z^2, z^2c, w, \dots, uvtwz^2c\}$$

$$E(\mathbb{F}_{p^2}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^4}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^8}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{16}}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{48}}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{96}})$$

$$(x_1, y_1) \rightarrow (x_2, y_2) \rightarrow (x_3, y_3) \rightarrow (x_4, y_4) \rightarrow (x_5, y_5) \rightarrow (x_5, cy_5)$$

$$(x, uy) \rightarrow (x, uvy) \rightarrow (x, uvt) \rightarrow (x, uvtw) \rightarrow (zx, uvtwzy)$$

$$\rightarrow (zx, uvtwzcy)$$

$$P_6 = (x_6, y_6) = (zx, uvtwzcy) = (za, uvtwzcb)_{B_{96}}$$

$$= ((0, 0, a, 0, \dots, 0), (0, \dots, 0, b, 0, 0))$$

• Path 3: Let

$$\mathbb{F}_{p^2} = \mathbb{F}_p[u]/(u^2 - \beta) \text{ such that } \beta \text{ non square}$$

$$\mathbb{F}_{p^4} = \mathbb{F}_{p^2}[v]/(v^2 - u) \text{ such that } u \text{ non square}$$

$$\mathbb{F}_{p^8} = \mathbb{F}_{p^4}[t]/(t^2 - v) \text{ such that } v \text{ non square}$$

$$\mathbb{F}_{p^{24}} = \mathbb{F}_{p^8}[w]/(w^3 - t) \text{ such that } t \text{ non cube}$$

$$\mathbb{F}_{p^{48}} = \mathbb{F}_{p^{24}}[z]/(z^2 - w) \text{ such that } w \text{ non square}$$

$$\mathbb{F}_{p^{96}} = \mathbb{F}_{p^{48}}[c]/(c^2 - z) \text{ such that } z \text{ non square}$$

Hence, $c^2 = z, z^2 = w, w^3 = t, t^2 = v$ and $v^2 = u$, so, $c^{48} = z^{24} = w^{12} = t^4 = v^2 = u$, so,

$$B_{96} = \{1, c, c^2, \dots, c^{95}\}$$

$$= \{1, c, z, zc, w, \dots, uvtw^2zc\}$$

$$E(\mathbb{F}_{p^2}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^4}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^8}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{24}}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{48}}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{96}})$$

$$(x_1, y_1) \rightarrow (x_2, y_2) \rightarrow (x_3, y_3) \rightarrow (x_4, y_4) \rightarrow (x_5, y_5) \rightarrow (x_5, cy_5)$$

$$(x, uy) \rightarrow (x, uvy) \rightarrow (x, uvt) \rightarrow (wx, uvtw) \rightarrow (wx, uvtwzy)$$

$$\rightarrow (wx, uvtwzcy)$$

$$P_6 = (x_6, y_6) = (wx, uvtwzcy) = (wa, uvtwzcb)_{B_{96}}$$

$$= ((0, 0, 0, 0, a, 0, \dots, 0), (0, \dots, 0, b, 0, 0, 0, 0))$$

• Path 4: Let

$$\mathbb{F}_{p^2} = \mathbb{F}_p[u]/(u^2 - \beta) \text{ such that } \beta \text{ non square}$$

$$\mathbb{F}_{p^4} = \mathbb{F}_{p^2}[v]/(v^2 - u) \text{ such that } u \text{ non square}$$

$$\mathbb{F}_{p^{12}} = \mathbb{F}_{p^4}[t]/(t^3 - v) \text{ such that } v \text{ non cube}$$

$$\mathbb{F}_{p^{24}} = \mathbb{F}_{p^8}[w]/(w^2 - t) \text{ such that } t \text{ non square}$$

$$\mathbb{F}_{p^{48}} = \mathbb{F}_{p^{16}}[z]/(z^2 - w) \text{ such that } w \text{ non square}$$

$$\mathbb{F}_{p^{96}} = \mathbb{F}_{p^{48}}[c]/(c^2 - z) \text{ such that } z \text{ non square}$$

Hence, $c^3 = z, z^2 = w, w^2 = t, t^3 = v$ and $v^2 = u$, so, $c^{48} = z^{24} = w^{12} = t^6 = v^2 = u$, so,

$$B_{96} = \{1, c, c^2, \dots, c^{95}\}$$

$$= \{1, c, z, zc, w, \dots, uvt^2wzc\}$$

$$E(\mathbb{F}_{p^2}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^4}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{12}}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{24}}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{48}}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{96}})$$

$$(x_1, y_1) \rightarrow (x_2, y_2) \rightarrow (x_3, y_3) \rightarrow (x_4, y_4) \rightarrow (x_5, y_5) \rightarrow (x_5, cy_5)$$

$$(x, uy) \rightarrow (x, uvy) \rightarrow (tx, uvt) \rightarrow (tx, uvtw) \rightarrow (tx, uvtwzy)$$

$$\rightarrow (tx, uvtwzcy)$$

$$P_6 = (x_6, y_6) = (tx, uvtwzcy) = (ta, uvtwzcb)_{B_{96}}$$

$$= ((0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, a, 0, \dots, 0), (0, \dots, 0, b, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0))$$

• Path 5: Let

$$\mathbb{F}_{p^2} = \mathbb{F}_p[u]/(u^2 - \beta) \text{ such that } \beta \text{ non square}$$

$$\mathbb{F}_{p^6} = \mathbb{F}_{p^2}[v]/(v^3 - u) \text{ such that } u \text{ non cube}$$

$$\mathbb{F}_{p^{12}} = \mathbb{F}_{p^6}[t]/(t^2 - v) \text{ such that } v \text{ non square}$$

$$\mathbb{F}_{p^{24}} = \mathbb{F}_{p^{12}}[w]/(w^2 - t) \text{ such that } t \text{ non square}$$

$$\mathbb{F}_{p^{48}} = \mathbb{F}_{p^{24}}[z]/(z^2 - w) \text{ such that } w \text{ non square}$$

$$\mathbb{F}_{p^{96}} = \mathbb{F}_{p^{48}}[c]/(c^2 - z) \text{ such that } z \text{ non square}$$

Hence, $c^3 = z, z^2 = w, w^2 = t, t^2 = v$ and $v^2 = u$, so, $c^{48} = z^{16} = w^8 = t^4 = v^2 = u$, so,

$$B_{96} = \{1, c, c^2, \dots, c^{95}\}$$

$$= \{1, c, z, zc, w, \dots, uv^2twzc\}$$

$$E(\mathbb{F}_{p^2}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^6}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{12}}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{24}}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{48}}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{96}})$$

$$(x_1, y_1) \rightarrow (x_2, y_2) \rightarrow (x_3, y_3) \rightarrow (x_4, y_4) \rightarrow (x_5, y_5) \rightarrow (x_5, cy_5)$$

$$(x, uy) \rightarrow (vx, uvy) \rightarrow (vx, uvt) \rightarrow (vx, uvtw) \rightarrow (vx, uvtwzy)$$

$$\rightarrow (vx, uvtwzcy)$$

$$P_6 = (x_6, y_6) = (vx, uvtwzcy) = (va, uvtwzcb)_{B_{96}}$$

$$= ((0, \dots, 0, a_{17}, 0, \dots, 0), (0, \dots, 0, b_{78}, 0, \dots, 0))$$

• Path 6: Let

$$\mathbb{F}_{p^3} = \mathbb{F}_p[u]/(u^3 - \beta) \text{ such that } \beta \text{ non cube}$$

$$\mathbb{F}_{p^6} = \mathbb{F}_{p^3}[v]/(v^2 - u) \text{ such that } u \text{ non square}$$

$$\mathbb{F}_{p^{12}} = \mathbb{F}_{p^6}[t]/(t^2 - v) \text{ such that } v \text{ non square}$$

$$\mathbb{F}_{p^{24}} = \mathbb{F}_{p^{12}}[w]/(w^2 - t) \text{ such that } t \text{ non square}$$

$$\mathbb{F}_{p^{48}} = \mathbb{F}_{p^{24}}[z]/(z^2 - w) \text{ such that } w \text{ non square}$$

$$\mathbb{F}_{p^{96}} = \mathbb{F}_{p^{48}}[c]/(c^2 - z) \text{ such that } c \text{ non square}$$

Hence, $c^2 = z, z^2 = w, w^2 = t, t^2 = v$ and $v^2 = u$, so, $I_{96} = (I_{48})_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = (997m + i)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = 997M_2 + I_2 = 2995m + i$.
 $c^{32} = z^{16} = w^8 = t^4 = v^2 = u$, so,

$$B_{96} = \{1, c, c^2, \dots, c^{95}\}$$

$$= \{1, c, z, zc, w, \dots, u^2vtwzc\}$$

$$E(\mathbb{F}_{p^3}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^6}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{12}}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{24}}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{48}}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{96}})$$

$$(x_1, y_1) \rightarrow (x_2, y_2) \rightarrow (x_3, y_3) \rightarrow (x_4, y_4) \rightarrow (x_5, y_5) \rightarrow (x_5, cy_5)$$

$$(ux, uy) \rightarrow (ux, uvy) \rightarrow (ux, uvt y) \rightarrow (ux, uvtwy) \rightarrow (ux, uvtwzy) \rightarrow (ux, uvtwzcy)$$

$$P_6 = (x_6, y_6) = (ux, uvtwzc) = (ua, uvtwzcb)_{B_{96}}$$

$$= ((0, \dots, 0, a_{33}, 0, \dots, 0), (0, \dots, 0, b_{62}, 0, \dots, 0))$$

Each rational point $P_6 \in E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{96}})$ has a special vector representation with 96 elements in \mathbb{F}_p for each x_6 and y_6 coordinates.

The cost of operations in in the 96th twisted field $\mathbb{F}_{p^{96}}$ are:

• First path:

$$E(\mathbb{F}_{p^2}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^4}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^8}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{16}}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{32}}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{96}})$$

$$M_{96} = (M_{32})_{\mathbb{F}_{p^3}} = (243m)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^3}} = 243M_3 = 1458m,$$

$$S_{96} = (S_{32})_{\mathbb{F}_{p^3}} = (162m)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^3}} = 162M_3 = 972m,$$

$$I_{96} = (I_{32})_{\mathbb{F}_{p^3}} = (484m + i)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^3}} = 484M_3 + I_3 = 2913m + 2s + i.$$

• Second path:

$$E(\mathbb{F}_{p^2}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^4}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^8}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{16}}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{48}}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{96}})$$

$$M_{96} = (M_{48})_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = (486m)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = 486M_2 = 1458m,$$

$$S_{96} = (S_{48})_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = (324m)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = 324M_2 = 972m,$$

$$I_{96} = (I_{48})_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = (969m + 2s + i)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = 969M_2 + 2S_2 + I_2 = 2915m + i.$$

• Third path:

$$E(\mathbb{F}_{p^2}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^4}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^8}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{24}}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{48}}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{96}})$$

$$M_{96} = (M_{48})_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = (486m)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = 486M_2 = 1458m,$$

$$S_{96} = (S_{48})_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = (324m)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = 324M_2 = 972m,$$

$$I_{96} = (I_{48})_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = (971m + i)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = 971M_2 + I_2 = 2917m + i.$$

• Fourth path:

$$E(\mathbb{F}_{p^2}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^4}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{12}}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{24}}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{48}}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{96}})$$

$$M_{96} = (M_{48})_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = (486m)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = 486M_2 = 1458m,$$

$$S_{96} = (S_{48})_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = (324m)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = 324M_2 = 972m,$$

$$I_{96} = (I_{48})_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = (977m + i)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = 977M_2 + I_2 = 2935m + i.$$

• Fifth path:

$$E(\mathbb{F}_{p^2}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^6}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{12}}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{24}}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{48}}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{96}})$$

$$M_{96} = (M_{48})_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = (486m)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = 486M_2 = 1458m,$$

$$S_{96} = (S_{48})_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = (324m)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = 324M_2 = 972m,$$

$$I_{96} = (I_{48})_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = (979m + i)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = 979M_2 + I_2 = 2941m + i.$$

• Sixth path:

$$E(\mathbb{F}_{p^3}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^6}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{12}}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{24}}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{48}}) \rightarrow E(\mathbb{F}_{p^{96}})$$

$$M_{96} = (M_{48})_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = (486m)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = 486M_2 = 1458m,$$

$$S_{96} = (S_{48})_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = (270m)_{\mathbb{F}_{p^2}} = 270M_2 = 810m,$$

TABLE V
COST OF OPERATIONS IN THE 96th TWISTED CURVE

	Field	Operations	$M_{2^i \cdot 3}$	$S_{2^i \cdot 3}$	Cost of $I_{2^i \cdot 3}$
1	$\mathbb{F}_{p^{96}}$	M_{96}, S_{96}, I_{96}	1458m	972m	2913m+2s+i
2	$\mathbb{F}_{p^{96}}$	M_{96}, S_{96}, I_{96}	1458m	972m	2915m+i
3	$\mathbb{F}_{p^{96}}$	M_{96}, S_{96}, I_{96}	1458m	972m	2917m+i
4	$\mathbb{F}_{p^{96}}$	M_{96}, S_{96}, I_{96}	1458m	972m	2935m+i
5	$\mathbb{F}_{p^{96}}$	M_{96}, S_{96}, I_{96}	1458m	972m	2941m+i
6	$\mathbb{F}_{p^{96}}$	M_{96}, S_{96}, I_{96}	1458m	810m	2995m+i

In the table above, we see that the cost of squaring in path 6 is less than the path 1, however the cost of inversion is more than path 1, after we subtract the overall cost of all operations, we find that the optimal path in this elliptic curve with embedding degree 96 is the sixth path.

Comparison

Table 11. Cost of operations in each the tower fields with embedding degree $2^i \cdot 3$

Field	Operations	Cost of $M_{2^i \cdot 3}$	Cost of $S_{2^i \cdot 3}$	Cost of $I_{2^i \cdot 3}$
\mathbb{F}_{p^6}	M_6, S_6, I_6	18m	10m	35m+i
$\mathbb{F}_{p^{12}}$	M_{12}, S_{12}, I_{12}	54m	30m	109m+i
$\mathbb{F}_{p^{24}}$	M_{24}, S_{24}, I_{24}	162m	90m	331m+i
$\mathbb{F}_{p^{48}}$	M_{48}, S_{48}, I_{48}	486m	270m	997m+i
$\mathbb{F}_{p^{96}}$	M_{96}, S_{96}, I_{96}	1458m	810m	2995m+i

In the table above, we take the optimal path based on the minimal squaring cost, we see that in the optimal path the cost of squaring is reduce by $1/6 \simeq 17\%$, and also we find a relationship between the operation cost and embedding degree $2^i \cdot 3$ as describe below

The cost of multiplication in elliptic curve with embedding degree $2^i \cdot 3$ is:

$$M_{2^i \cdot 3} = 3^i \cdot 6m$$

The cost of squaring in elliptic curve with embedding degree $2^i \cdot 3$ is:

$$S_{2^i \cdot 3} = 2.5 \cdot 3^{i-1} m$$

The cost of inversion in elliptic curve with embedding degree 2^i is:

$$I_{2^i \cdot 3} = (31 \cdot 3^{i-1} + \sum_1^i 4 \cdot 3^{i-1})m + i$$

Proof 1: By recurrence relation we will prove the above formulas.

- For $i=1$ we have $M_6 = 18m, S_6 = 10m$ and $I_6 = 35m + i$, and that is correct.
- Let for $i=n$ $M_{2^n \cdot 3} = 3^n \cdot 6m, S_{2^n \cdot 3} = 2.5 \cdot 3^{n-1} m$ and $I_{2^n \cdot 3} = (31 \cdot 3^{n-1} + \sum_1^n 4 \cdot 3^{i-1})m + i$ are correct.
- We will prove the same for $i=n+1$ are also correct,

We have: $M_{2^{n+1}.3} = M_{2^n.3.2} = (M_{2^n.3})_{\mathbb{F}_2} = 3^n.6M_2 = 3^{n+1}.6m.$

$$S_{2^{n+1}.3} = S_{2^n.3.2} = (S_{2^n.3})_{\mathbb{F}_2} = 2.5.3^{n-1}M_2 \\ = 2.5.3^{n-1}.3m = 2.5.3^n m.$$

$$I_{2^{n+1}.3} = I_{2^n.3.2} = (I_{2^n.3})_{\mathbb{F}_2} \\ = (31.3^{n-1} + \sum_{1}^n 4.3^{n-1})M_2 + I_2 \\ = (31.3^{n-1} + \sum_{1}^n 4.3^{n-1})3m + 4m + i \\ = (31.3^n + \sum_{2}^{n+1} 4.3^{n-1})m + 4m + i \\ = (31.3^n + \sum_{1}^{n+1} 4.3^{n-1})m + i$$

```
# Define the base field F_p and the non-cube element beta
p = next_prime(10^6) # You can choose an appropriate prime
F_p = GF(p)
beta = randint(1, p-1) # Choose a non-cube element
# Define the extension field F_{p^3}
a = randint(1, p-1) # a random integer
while beta != a^3:
    F_{p^3} = F_p.extension(u^3 - beta)
u_0 = F_{p^3}.gen()
# Construct the extension fields and elliptic curve points
# Construct the points (a_i, b_j)_{B_{2^i.3}}
E_points = []
for i in range(1, 6):
    u_i = F_{p^3}.gen()
    alpha_i = randint(1, p^{2^i-1}.3)-1
    while alpha_i^2 != u_i:
        F_{p^3} = F_{p^3}.extension(u_i^2 - u_{i-1})
        x_i = x.u_{i-1} = a_{2^i-1}
        y_i = y.prod(u_i) = b_{2^i-1}.3-1.2^{i-1}
        P_i = (x_i, y_i)
    # Calculate M_{2^i.3}, S_{2^i.3}, and I_{2^i.3}
    M_{2^i.3} = 3^i * 6 * m
    S_{2^i.3} = 2 * 5 * 3^{i-1} * m
    I_{2^i.3} = (31 * 3^{i-1} + sum([4 * 3^{i-1} for _ in range(1, i+1)])) * m + i
# Append the constructed points and parameters to the list
E_points.append((B_{2^i.3}, M_{2^i.3}, S_{2^i.3}, I_{2^i.3}))
# Display the results
print("The extension field F_{p^3} is F_{p^3}=", F_{p^3})
print("The point P_i is P_i=" P_i)
print("The cost of multiplication is M_{2^i.3}=" M_{2^i.3})
print("The cost of squaring is S_{2^i.3}=" S_{2^i.3})
print("The cost of inversion is I_{2^i.3}=" I_{2^i.3})
```

Remark 2: In every vector point representation, we see that each point $P = (a_i, b_j)$ with i and j are the position of points a and b in the base B_k , we have $i + j = k - 1$ with k is the embedding degree of the finite finite, so we can know the vector point representation with only the one element, so we can reduce 50% of the time, with no further arithmetic operation.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we present efficient methods for building towers of finite field extensions of the form $2^i.3 < 100$ for use in cryptography (pairing and isogenie). We break down our work into three constructions: First, we employ the tower building technique and examine all path possible, Second, we compute the cost of the arithmetic operations in \mathbb{F}_{p^6} , $\mathbb{F}_{p^{12}}$, $\mathbb{F}_{p^{24}}$, $\mathbb{F}_{p^{48}}$, and $\mathbb{F}_{p^{96}}$. Finally, by analyzing these costs, we are able to find the optimal path in these finite extensions fields, leading to better performance in cryptographic applications.

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